

VIP ARES Control Team 2026 Spring Group Paper

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Abstract—Autonomous racing is a challenging control problem because the vehicle must drive fast while still maintaining stability, safety, and accurate trajectory tracking. In a racing environment, the problem becomes more complicated when multiple vehicles are involved, since each car may need to consider not only its own performance but also team strategy, opponent behavior, and shared racing objectives. This two-semester project studies autonomous racing from both a controller design perspective and a multi-agent strategy perspective.

The project first focused on low-level vehicle control, including PID-based control and ADRC-based exploration for improving tracking performance and robustness. As the project developed, the focus gradually moved toward optimal control methods, especially LQR and MPC, because these methods provide a clearer way to connect tracking error, control effort, stability, and strategy-dependent priorities. In the second stage of the project, a hierarchical racing strategy framework was introduced. This framework connects high-level team objectives, mid-level tactical decisions, and low-level controller execution. A consensus-inspired multi-agent structure was also considered to describe cooperation between vehicles and the influence of team-level strategy on individual vehicle behavior.

Through modeling, simulation, and controller comparison, this project shows that autonomous racing should not be treated only as a path-tracking problem. Instead, it can be viewed as a strategy-driven multi-agent control problem. The results suggest that LQR and MPC are promising choices for this type of framework because they can naturally include performance weights, constraints, and strategy-related objectives.

I. INTRODUCTION

Autonomous racing has become an important test platform for studying advanced control, planning, and autonomous decision-making. Compared with normal autonomous driving, racing usually happens at higher speed and closer to the vehicle's physical limits. A racing vehicle must track a desired path, keep stable motion, respond to changing conditions, and avoid unsafe behavior near other vehicles. Because of these challenges, autonomous racing is a useful environment for testing control algorithms before applying similar ideas to more general autonomous systems.

Most basic vehicle control problems focus on how to make one vehicle follow a reference trajectory. In that setting, common objectives include reducing lateral error, reducing heading error, improving stability, and limiting the control input. These objectives are still very important in racing. However, racing also includes a larger decision-making problem. A vehicle may need to decide whether to drive aggressively or conservatively, whether to protect its position, how to cooperate with a teammate, and how to react to an opponent. Therefore, racing performance cannot be fully explained by tracking accuracy alone. It also depends on strategy, cooperation, risk preference, and the way high-level decisions are passed down to the controller.

This project started from this basic control viewpoint and gradually moved toward a larger strategy-based framework. In the first stage, the main focus was on low-level controller design. PID control was used as a simple and intuitive baseline, while ADRC was explored as a more robust method for handling uncertainty and disturbance. These controllers helped us understand the basic tracking and stability requirements of an autonomous racing vehicle. However, as the project continued, we found that low-level control alone was not enough to describe the whole racing problem. A controller can make the car follow a path, but it does not directly explain how the vehicle should behave under different racing strategies.

For this reason, the second stage of the project introduced LQR, MPC, and a hierarchical racing strategy framework. LQR is useful because it allows the control objective to be written as a cost function that balances tracking performance and control effort. MPC goes one step further by considering prediction and constraints over a future time horizon. These two methods are especially suitable for a strategy-aware racing problem because their weights, objectives, and constraints can be adjusted according to different racing goals. For example, an aggressive strategy may place more weight on speed and overtaking opportunity, while a conservative strategy may place more weight on stability and safety margin.

Another important part of this project is the multi-agent

racing structure. In a real racing scenario, vehicles do not act independently. A car may need to share information with a teammate, maintain a useful formation, block an opponent, or sacrifice its own short-term optimal action for a better team result. To describe this idea, we considered a consensus-inspired strategy layer. In this layer, team-level goals and vehicle relationships can influence the behavior of each individual car. This does not mean that the vehicles must always do the same thing. Instead, consensus is used as a way to describe how multiple vehicles can coordinate toward a shared racing objective while still keeping their own roles.

The main idea of this paper is that autonomous racing can be modeled as a hierarchical multi-agent control problem. At the top level, the team or system defines the racing objective. At the middle level, the objective is translated into tactical decisions such as role assignment, risk level, and cooperation strategy. At the bottom level, controllers such as PID, ADRC, LQR, and MPC execute the desired motion. This structure provides a clearer connection between racing strategy and controller design.

The contributions of this project can be summarized in three parts. First, we developed a hierarchical framework that connects racing strategy, tactical planning, and low-level control. Second, we extended the controller design from PID and ADRC to LQR and MPC, which are more suitable for objective-based and constraint-aware racing control. Third, we proposed a simulation-based evaluation structure to compare controllers using tracking accuracy, stability, control effort, and strategy consistency. The goal of this project is not to claim a complete racing system, but to build a clear foundation for future work in autonomous racing strategy and multi-agent control.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the project background and motivation. Section 3 gives an overview of the system structure. Section 4 presents the multi-agent racing strategy framework. Section 5 discusses controller design and integration. Section 6 describes the simulation setup and evaluation method. Sections 7 and 8 discuss the challenges, limitations, and future work. Finally, Section 9 concludes the paper.

II. PROJECT BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

This project was developed as a two-semester undergraduate research project on autonomous racing and controller design. At the beginning, our main question was relatively direct: how can we design a controller that allows an autonomous racing vehicle to follow a desired trajectory with good stability and reasonable control effort? From this starting point, we first studied basic vehicle control methods. PID control was used as a baseline because it is simple, intuitive, and easy to tune. We also explored ADRC as a more robust control method, especially for cases where the system may have uncertainty or disturbance. This first stage helped us understand the basic requirements of autonomous racing, such as path tracking, heading correction, stability, and controller response.

As the project continued, we realized that racing is not only a low-level tracking problem. A controller can reduce tracking error, but it does not directly explain how the car should behave under different racing objectives. For example, an aggressive racing strategy may allow the vehicle to take more risk in order to improve speed or overtaking opportunity. A conservative strategy may place more importance on stability, safety margin, and avoiding large control actions. In a multi-vehicle scenario, the problem becomes even more complicated because the best action for one vehicle may not always be the best action for the whole team. This observation pushed the project from a single-vehicle control viewpoint toward a larger racing system viewpoint.

Because of this change in perspective, we introduced LQR and MPC as the next step after PID and ADRC. LQR is useful because it describes the control objective through a cost function. Instead of only tuning gains directly, we can assign weights to tracking error, heading error, state deviation, and control effort. This makes the controller more connected to the overall performance objective. MPC extends this idea further by using prediction over a future time horizon and by allowing constraints to be included more naturally. For autonomous racing, these constraints may include track boundaries, actuator limits, safety margins, and interaction with other vehicles. Therefore, LQR and MPC provide a more structured way to connect controller behavior with racing objectives.

Another important motivation of this project was to introduce a strategy layer above the controller. In real racing, the vehicle is not only trying to follow a path. It also needs to understand the racing goal, the role of each vehicle, the risk preference, and the relationship between teammates and opponents. For this reason, we considered a hierarchical racing framework. In this framework, the top layer represents the team or racing objective, the middle layer translates this objective into tactical decisions, and the bottom layer executes the motion through the controller. This structure allows the controller to be guided by a larger strategy instead of acting only as an isolated tracking system.

We also considered a consensus-inspired multi-agent structure to describe cooperation between vehicles. In this project, consensus does not mean that all cars should behave in exactly the same way. Instead, it means that different vehicles can coordinate under a shared racing objective while still keeping different roles. For example, one vehicle may focus on maintaining speed, while another vehicle may support team positioning or defensive behavior. By using a consensus-inspired idea, team-level strategy can influence individual vehicle decisions through weights, constraints, or shared performance objectives.

The overall development of the project is shown in Fig. 1. The main evolution was from asking how to control one racing vehicle to asking how multiple autonomous racing vehicles should behave under different racing strategies. This transition helped us connect controller design, strategy planning, and multi-agent cooperation into one project framework. The project is still mainly simulation-based, but it provides a clear

Project Evolution: From Controller Design to Strategy-Driven Autonomous Racing

Two-semester development of the project idea, methods, and system framework

Fig. 1. Evolution of the project idea from low-level controller design to a strategy-driven multi-agent autonomous racing framework.

foundation for future work involving more realistic vehicle models, hardware testing, and real racing scenarios.

III. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

In this project, the autonomous racing system is organized as a hierarchical closed-loop framework. Instead of viewing the controller as an isolated path-tracking tool, we place it inside a larger system that includes racing objectives, strategy decisions, tactical planning, vehicle dynamics, and feedback from the environment. The main goal of this framework is to connect high-level racing intention with low-level vehicle execution in a clear and structured way. This is also the main reason why the project gradually moved from basic controller design to a strategy-driven autonomous racing framework.

A. Overall Architecture

The overall system structure is shown in Fig. 2. At the top level, the system receives information from the racing environment, including the track map, the team objective, vehicle measurements, and the states of teammates or opponents. Based on these inputs, the strategy layer determines the high-level behavior of the system. Typical strategy variables include whether the vehicle should behave aggressively or conservatively, how much weight should be given to team

cooperation, and what level of risk is acceptable in the current racing situation.

The output of the strategy layer is then passed to the planning or tactical layer. This layer translates abstract racing goals into more concrete commands, such as the reference path, reference speed, role assignment, and safety margin. In other words, the planning layer acts as the bridge between the racing objective and the controller. Once these reference quantities are generated, the control layer computes the actual control input to the vehicle. In our project, this control layer may use PID, ADRC, LQR, or MPC, depending on the controller being tested. Finally, the vehicle dynamics and simulation block updates the vehicle motion and produces measurable outputs for evaluation.

B. Vehicle Quantities and Control Variables

To describe the racing vehicle mathematically, we define the state of vehicle i as

$$x_i = [p_i \ v_i \ \psi_i \ e_{y,i} \ e_{\psi,i}]^T, \quad (1)$$

where p_i denotes the position of the vehicle on the track, v_i is the longitudinal speed, ψ_i is the heading angle, $e_{y,i}$ is the lateral tracking error, and $e_{\psi,i}$ is the heading error with respect to the reference path.

System Overview of the Proposed Autonomous Racing Framework

Fig. 2. System overview of the proposed autonomous racing framework. The framework connects racing objectives, strategy decisions, tactical planning, controller execution, and simulation-based vehicle dynamics in one closed-loop structure.

The measured output is written as

$$y_i = [p_i \quad v_i \quad \psi_i \quad e_{y,i} \quad e_{\psi,i}]^T, \quad (2)$$

which means that, in our simulation framework, the main performance variables are directly observable and can be used for feedback and evaluation.

The control input of vehicle i is defined as

$$u_i = [\delta_i \quad a_i]^T, \quad (3)$$

where δ_i is the steering command and a_i is the longitudinal acceleration or braking command. This form is general enough for PID, ADRC, LQR, and MPC, and it provides a common interface for comparing different controllers under the same racing task.

Since the controller should not work alone, we also define a reference command generated by the upper layers:

$$r_i = [\mathcal{P}_i^{\text{ref}} \quad v_i^{\text{ref}} \quad \rho_i \quad d_i^{\text{safe}}]^T, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathcal{P}_i^{\text{ref}}$ is the reference path, v_i^{ref} is the reference speed, ρ_i is the role or tactical assignment of the vehicle, and d_i^{safe} is the safety margin. This vector collects the main planning results that are passed to the controller.

At the strategy level, we use a higher-level decision variable

$$s_i = [m_i \quad c_i \quad \eta_i]^T, \quad (5)$$

where m_i represents the driving mode (for example, aggressive or conservative), c_i represents the cooperation policy, and η_i represents the risk preference or strategy weight. The exact form of these variables may change depending on the racing scenario, but this notation is useful because it shows clearly that the controller is guided by a larger decision-making structure.

With these definitions, the closed-loop vehicle update can be described in a general form as

$$x_i(k+1) = f_i(x_i(k), u_i(k), w_i(k)), \quad (6)$$

where $f_i(\cdot)$ represents the vehicle dynamics and simulation model, and $w_i(k)$ represents disturbance or interaction terms caused by the environment or other vehicles. The control input is generated by

$$u_i(k) = \pi_i(x_i(k), r_i(k), s_i(k)), \quad (7)$$

where $\pi_i(\cdot)$ denotes the controller, which can be PID, ADRC, LQR, or MPC. Equation (7) is important because it shows that

the controller depends not only on the current state, but also on the reference command and the racing strategy.

C. Information Flow and Closed-Loop Control Loop

The information flow of the whole system is shown in Fig. 3. The system first receives external and internal information, including track geometry, current vehicle states, teammate or opponent information, and the team strategy. These inputs are processed by the strategy and tactical decision block, which generates reference commands for the controller. The controller then computes the control input u_i and sends it to the vehicle or plant. After the vehicle dynamics are updated, the measurable outputs y_i are fed back to both the controller and the upper decision-making layers.

This closed-loop structure is one of the key differences between the current project and a more traditional controller-only design. In earlier stages of the project, the main question was how to make the vehicle follow a path well. In the current framework, the controller still performs that task, but it is no longer the whole system. It becomes one component inside a larger loop where information from strategy, planning, and vehicle feedback all influence the final control action.

From the system point of view, the information flow can be summarized in three steps. First, the racing context determines the strategic objective. Second, the strategic objective is translated into tactical references and constraints. Third, the controller uses these references together with the measured state to generate the control input. This structure makes it possible to compare different controllers under the same high-level objective, and it also provides a natural way to study how changes in racing strategy affect vehicle behavior.

In summary, the proposed system provides a unified framework for autonomous racing. It clearly defines the main state variables, control inputs, measured outputs, and reference commands, while also explaining how information moves across the strategy, planning, and control layers. This overall structure supports the rest of the paper: Section IV will further discuss the multi-agent racing strategy framework, Section V will describe the controller design in more detail, and Section VI will present the simulation and evaluation results.

IV. MULTI-AGENT RACING STRATEGY FRAMEWORK

After defining the overall system structure, the next step is to describe how the racing problem changes when more than one vehicle is involved. In a single-vehicle problem, the main goal is usually to track a reference path while keeping the vehicle stable. In a multi-agent racing problem, each vehicle still needs to track its own reference, but it also needs to consider other vehicles, team objectives, and possible cooperation or competition. Therefore, the strategy layer should not be treated as a separate idea from control. It should provide useful information to the planning and control layers.

In this project, the multi-agent racing framework is used to describe how different vehicles exchange information and respond to a shared racing objective. The goal is not to build a

complete professional racing strategy solver. Instead, the goal is to create a clear structure that connects multi-agent strategy, consensus-inspired cooperation, and controller design.

A. State Definition and Constraints

Consider a racing scenario with N autonomous vehicles. The set of vehicles is denoted as

$$\mathcal{V} = \{1, 2, \dots, N\}. \quad (8)$$

For vehicle $i \in \mathcal{V}$, the state is written as

$$x_i(k) = [p_i(k) \quad v_i(k) \quad \psi_i(k) \quad e_{y,i}(k) \quad e_{\psi,i}(k)]^T, \quad (9)$$

where $p_i(k)$ represents the position of the vehicle on the track, $v_i(k)$ is the speed, $\psi_i(k)$ is the heading angle, $e_{y,i}(k)$ is the lateral tracking error, and $e_{\psi,i}(k)$ is the heading error. The control input is defined as

$$u_i(k) = [\delta_i(k) \quad a_i(k)]^T, \quad (10)$$

where $\delta_i(k)$ is the steering input and $a_i(k)$ is the acceleration or braking command.

The full multi-agent state and input can be collected as

$$X(k) = [x_1^T(k) \quad x_2^T(k) \quad \dots \quad x_N^T(k)]^T, \quad (11)$$

and

$$U(k) = [u_1^T(k) \quad u_2^T(k) \quad \dots \quad u_N^T(k)]^T. \quad (12)$$

The racing vehicles must satisfy several basic constraints. First, each vehicle should remain inside the track boundary:

$$p_i(k) \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (13)$$

where \mathcal{T} represents the feasible track region. The vehicle speed and acceleration are also limited by physical constraints:

$$0 \leq v_i(k) \leq v_{\max}, \quad (14)$$

$$a_{\min} \leq a_i(k) \leq a_{\max}. \quad (15)$$

The steering input is bounded as

$$|\delta_i(k)| \leq \delta_{\max}. \quad (16)$$

In a multi-vehicle racing environment, collision avoidance is also important. For two different vehicles i and j , a simple safety constraint can be written as

$$\|p_i(k) - p_j(k)\|_2 \geq d_{\min}, \quad i \neq j, \quad (17)$$

where d_{\min} is the minimum safe distance. In this project, these constraints provide a basic mathematical description of the racing environment. Some controllers, such as MPC, can include these constraints more directly. Other controllers, such as PID or LQR, can still be evaluated based on how well they respect these constraints in simulation.

Information Flow and Closed-Loop Control Structure

Fig. 3. Information flow and closed-loop control structure of the autonomous racing framework. The controller is placed inside a larger strategy-driven loop instead of acting only as a low-level path-tracking unit.

B. Information Sharing and Communication

The multi-agent racing system also depends on what information each vehicle can access. In this project, each vehicle has local information from its own sensors and controller. This includes its current state, tracking error, speed, heading, and control input. At the same time, a vehicle may also receive shared information from teammates, opponents, or a higher-level strategy layer. This shared information can include relative position, speed difference, role assignment, and current racing intention.

To describe this communication structure, we define a directed communication graph

$$\mathcal{G}_c = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}), \quad (18)$$

where \mathcal{V} is the set of vehicles and \mathcal{E} is the set of communication links. If vehicle i can receive information from vehicle j , then $(j, i) \in \mathcal{E}$. The neighbor set of vehicle i is defined as

$$\mathcal{N}_i = \{j \in \mathcal{V} \mid (j, i) \in \mathcal{E}\}. \quad (19)$$

The local and shared information available to vehicle i can be summarized as

$$\mathcal{I}_i(k) = \{x_i(k), u_i(k), r_i(k), x_j(k), z_j(k) \mid j \in \mathcal{N}_i\}, \quad (20)$$

where $r_i(k)$ is the reference command from the planning layer, and $z_j(k)$ represents the strategy state or racing intention of another vehicle. This notation shows that each vehicle is not only reacting to its own tracking error, but also responding to information from the surrounding racing system.

A simplified two-vehicle example is shown in Fig. 4. The figure illustrates the basic idea that both vehicles receive the same high-level racing objective, but they still keep their own states and control inputs. The vehicles exchange local information such as relative position, speed, and role intention. This information exchange supports coordination, but it does not require the vehicles to behave identically.

C. Hierarchical Strategy Structure

The strategy framework is organized into three levels: team objective, tactical planning, and control execution. The team objective layer defines the general racing goal. For example, the goal may be to drive aggressively, finish safely, protect a team position, or support another vehicle. We denote the team-level objective as

$$\gamma(k) \in \Gamma, \quad (21)$$

where Γ represents the set of possible racing objectives.

Fig. 4. Simplified two-vehicle interaction in the multi-agent racing strategy framework. The vehicles exchange local information while responding to a shared team objective.

The tactical planning layer converts the team objective into vehicle-level commands. For vehicle i , the reference command is written as

$$r_i(k) = [\mathcal{P}_i^{\text{ref}}(k) \quad v_i^{\text{ref}}(k) \quad \rho_i(k) \quad d_i^{\text{safe}}(k)]^T, \quad (22)$$

where $\mathcal{P}_i^{\text{ref}}(k)$ is the reference path, $v_i^{\text{ref}}(k)$ is the reference speed, $\rho_i(k)$ is the role assignment, and $d_i^{\text{safe}}(k)$ is the desired safety margin.

The control execution layer then uses the state, reference command, and strategy information to compute the control input:

$$u_i(k) = \pi_i(x_i(k), r_i(k), z_i(k)), \quad (23)$$

where $\pi_i(\cdot)$ represents the selected controller, such as PID, ADRC, LQR, or MPC. The strategy variable $z_i(k)$ is used to represent the racing intention of vehicle i . A simple form is

$$z_i(k) = [\alpha_i(k) \quad c_i(k) \quad \eta_i(k)]^T, \quad (24)$$

where $\alpha_i(k)$ represents aggressiveness, $c_i(k)$ represents cooperation level, and $\eta_i(k)$ represents risk preference.

The important idea is that strategy does not directly become a steering angle or acceleration command. Instead, strategy changes the reference, priority, weight, or constraint given to the controller. For example, an aggressive strategy may increase the reference speed or reduce the safety margin,

while a conservative strategy may reduce speed and place more weight on stability. In this way, the controller remains responsible for low-level execution, but the upper layer decides what kind of behavior the controller should support.

D. Consensus-Inspired Coordination

To describe cooperation between vehicles, we use a consensus-inspired update rule for the strategy state. A simple form is

$$z_i(k+1) = z_i(k) + \mu \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} w_{ij} (z_j(k) - z_i(k)) + \nu q_i(k), \quad (25)$$

where w_{ij} is the interaction weight between vehicle i and vehicle j , μ controls the strength of multi-agent coordination, $q_i(k)$ is the top-down strategy command from the team objective, and ν controls how strongly the team objective affects vehicle i .

This equation is not meant to make all vehicles behave in exactly the same way. In racing, identical behavior is usually not useful because vehicles may have different roles. Instead, the consensus-inspired term describes how the strategy of one vehicle is influenced by nearby vehicles. The top-down term $q_i(k)$ allows different vehicles to receive different role commands, so that the team can still coordinate while keeping individual behavior. For example, one vehicle may focus on maintaining speed, while another may focus on defensive positioning or supporting a teammate.

This is the main reason why consensus is useful in this project. It gives us a simple mathematical way to connect shared objectives and individual actions. It also creates a bridge between high-level racing strategy and controller-level behavior.

E. Cooperation and Competition in Racing

A realistic racing system includes both cooperation and competition. For teammates, the goal may be to improve the team result, share information, avoid interfering with each other, and follow a coordinated race plan. For opponents, the goal is different. The vehicle may need to protect its position, find an overtaking opportunity, or maintain a safe distance.

For teammate cooperation, we can define a simple team-level cost:

$$J_{\text{team}} = \sum_{i=1}^N J_i + \lambda_{\text{coop}} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{E}_{\text{team}}} \|z_i - z_j - \Delta_{ij}^{\text{role}}\|^2, \quad (26)$$

where J_i is the individual performance cost of vehicle i , λ_{coop} is the cooperation weight, and $\Delta_{ij}^{\text{role}}$ represents the desired difference between the roles of two vehicles. This term is useful because cooperation does not always mean both vehicles should do the same thing. Instead, it means their actions should be consistent with the team plan.

For opponent interaction, we can define a simplified competition-related cost for vehicle i :

$$J_{\text{opp},i} = \lambda_{\text{safe}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{O}_i} \phi(d_{ij}) - \lambda_{\text{adv}} A_i, \quad (27)$$

where \mathcal{O}_i is the set of opponent vehicles near vehicle i , $d_{ij} = \|p_i - p_j\|_2$ is the distance between vehicle i and opponent j , $\phi(d_{ij})$ is a penalty function that becomes large when the distance is too small, and A_i represents racing advantage such as position gain or overtaking opportunity. The first term encourages safety, while the second term represents the racing objective of gaining advantage.

The same multi-agent structure can therefore describe both cooperation and competition. The difference is how the interaction weights and cost terms are defined. For teammates, the interaction usually encourages coordination and consistency with the team strategy. For opponents, the interaction is more related to safety, blocking, overtaking, and relative position. This gives the framework enough flexibility to describe racing behavior without making the model too complicated.

Overall, this section defines the basic multi-agent racing strategy framework used in the project. The vehicle states, control inputs, constraints, communication graph, strategy variables, and consensus-inspired update rule together provide a structured way to connect racing strategy with controller design. The next section will focus on how different controllers can be integrated into this framework.

V. CONTROLLER DESIGN AND INTEGRATION

The controller design in this project follows a progressive structure from baseline feedback control to optimal control. We started by using a PID controller. Since PID controllers are relatively easy to design and are widely used in both industry and academia, they are considered the most reliable type of controller. The PID controller directly converts tracking errors into steering and acceleration commands, allowing us to directly observe the vehicle's turning and acceleration control. It also serves as a reference for the design of other controllers. However, autonomous racing is not only a simple tracking problem. The vehicle must reduce path-tracking error while also considering control effort, stability, safety, and racing objectives. For this reason, the project was extended from PID-based control to optimal control methods, especially Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR) and Model Predictive Control (MPC). These methods are more suitable for goal-driven racing because they formulate the control task as an optimization problem by using the cost function.

The general controller design idea can be summarized as

$$u^* = \arg \min_u (\text{tracking error} + \text{control effort} + \text{safety risk} + \text{strategy deviation}). \quad (28)$$

where the optimal control input is selected to best satisfy the current racing objective while respecting vehicle and safety limitations.

In this framework, PID serves as the baseline controller, while LQR and MPC are used to explore optimal control. LQR introduces a quadratic cost function to balance state regulation and control effort. MPC further extends this idea by predicting future system behavior over a finite horizon and allowing constraints to be included in the optimization problem. Therefore, the controller design is not only focused

on making the vehicle follow a reference path, but also on connecting low-level control actions with higher-level racing objectives.

A. PID Controller

In this project, we use PID as our baseline. We use PID control for the lateral dimension and PI control for the longitudinal dimension.

We can start the whole system with the tracking error:

$$e(t) = r(t) - y(t), \quad (29)$$

Here, $r(t)$ is the reference signal and $y(t)$ is the system output. Then, we can make a PID controller in the continuous time in a typical way.

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i \int_0^t e(\tau) d\tau + K_d \frac{de(t)}{dt}, \quad (30)$$

where K_p , K_i , and K_d are the proportional, integral, and derivative gains, respectively.

We chose to use a manual tuning method for these three variables. We followed a standard parameter tuning process. We started by setting all three parameters to 0, then fine-tuned K_i , K_p , and K_d one by one. We obtained satisfactory results, but the process was still largely experience-driven and requires further optimization.

B. LQR Controller

The Linear Quadratic Regulator, LQR, is an optimal state-feedback control method for linear dynamic systems. Its objective is to find a feedback control law that minimizes a quadratic cost function.

We can consider a discrete-time linear system,

$$x(k+1) = Ax(k) + Bu(k), \quad (31)$$

In this equation, $x(k)$ is the state. In our controller design, it can be the error we want to eliminate like lateral error and heading error etc. $u(k)$ is the control input, we can see it as the steering wheel or etc. And A and B are the system matrices, we can also relate these two variables to their physical meanings.

Then, we can define our cost function like this. And Q means how much we care about state and R means how much we care about input.

$$J = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} [x^T(k)Qx(k) + u^T(k)Ru(k)], \quad (32)$$

To get the best feedback control law, we can start with the Bellman equation. And we are calculating the minimum future cost starting from the current state.

$$V(x) = \min_u \{x^T Qx + u^T R u + V(Ax + Bu)\}. \quad (33)$$

After we give the $V(x)$ a standard form, we get:

$$x^T P x = \min_u \{x^T Q x + u^T R u + (Ax + Bu)^T P (Ax + Bu)\}. \quad (34)$$

Fig. 5. LQR design

Then, equation can be:

$$x^T P x = \min_u \{x^T Q x + u^T R u + x^T A^T P A x + 2x^T A^T P B u + u^T B^T P B u\}. \quad (35)$$

Then we derivative with respect to u , we can get the K value in feedback law. And we will have: Solving for u , the optimal control input is

$$u = -(R + B^T P B)^{-1} B^T P A x. \quad (36)$$

Thus, we will have the control law which is similar as a feedback control:

$$u = -Kx, \quad (37)$$

where the feedback gain is

$$K = (R + B^T P B)^{-1} B^T P A. \quad (38)$$

After we put the previous equation into the Bellman equation, we will get:

$$P = Q + A^T P A - A^T P B (R + B^T P B)^{-1} B^T P A. \quad (39)$$

C. MPC Controller

Model Predictive Control (MPC) is an advanced, optimization-based control strategy that uses a dynamic model of a process to predict future behavior over a finite time horizon. We can consider a discrete-time linear system which is almost same as the LQR controller.

$$x(k+1) = Ax(k) + Bu(k), \quad (40)$$

Same as LQR controller, $x(k)$ can be the error we want to eliminate like lateral error and heading error etc. $u(k)$ is the control input like the steering wheel or etc.

Since it's a kind of the optimal control, we have the cost function like:

$$J = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \left[x^T(k+i|k) Q x(k+i|k) + u^T(k+i|k) R u(k+i|k) \right] + x^T(k+N|k) F x(k+N|k). \quad (41)$$

In this equation, Q means how much we care about the error, R means how much we care about the input, and F means how much we care about the final state.

Fig. 6. MPC design

At time step k , We use the internal prediction model to get the prediction state in the prediction horizon N :

$$X_k = \begin{bmatrix} x(k+1|k) \\ x(k+2|k) \\ \vdots \\ x(k+N|k) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (42)$$

Meanwhile, we can get the future control sequence like:

$$U_k = \begin{bmatrix} u(k|k) \\ u(k+1|k) \\ \vdots \\ u(k+N-1|k) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (43)$$

Then, after using the discrete-time model again and again, we can get:

$$X_k = Mx(k) + CU_k, \quad (44)$$

where M describes the effect of the current state on the future trajectory, and C describes the effect of the future control sequence on the predicted states.

After that, we use the Quadratic programming to do the simplification for our cost function:

$$J = x^T(k) G x(k) + 2x^T(k) E U_k + U_k^T H U_k, \quad (45)$$

In this equation, we can see while the first term means the initial states, other two terms means the optimization. We can use Matlab to minimize this cost function. Which is like solving:

$$U_k^* = \arg \min_{U_k} J, \quad (46)$$

D. Strategy-Driven Controller Selection

To sum up, we are comparing three kinds of controllers and going to move them into the simulation tests. PID is used as the baseline controller. LQR is employed when efficient feedback optimization is required, while MPC is used when prediction and constraints are critical.

As for PID, it can directly convert the error into a control input. However, it does not have a specific cost function, cannot optimize future behavior, and its parameter tuning relies

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF CONTROLLERS USED IN THIS PROJECT

Controller	Core Idea	Strength	Limitation
PID	Error-based feedback	Simple and intuitive	No explicit optimization
LQR	Optimal state feedback	Efficient optimal feedback law	No explicit constraint handling
MPC	Online optimization over a finite horizon	Predictive and constraint-aware	Higher computational cost

heavily on experience. Furthermore, PID does not integrate well with strategies and is unable to execute requirements passed down from other layers.

LQR is a method based on optimal control. It effectively captures the requirements we pass down from other layers. Furthermore, since it is essentially a feedback control method, it achieves our objectives with minimal computational cost. However, it is less accurate than MPC and lacks certain constraints.

MPC does not merely consider the current error; instead, it predicts how the system will evolve over a future time horizon and then selects the control input accordingly. Furthermore, MPC effectively accounts for constraints, making the race car's operation safer. Although MPC is well-suited for race cars, the fact that an optimization problem must be solved at every step results in a significant computational load.

VI. SIMULATION AND EVALUATION

The purpose of the simulation is to evaluate whether a controller can execute a racing strategy, not only whether it can follow a reference path. In the earlier stage of the project, the simulation mainly focused on low-level trajectory tracking and vehicle stability. As the project developed, the simulation was extended to evaluate how different controllers support strategy-consistent behavior under the same racing objective. Therefore, the evaluation includes both traditional control performance and higher-level strategy execution performance.

A. Simulation Setup

The simulation is organized around a closed-loop autonomous racing task. A reference racing line is generated on a closed track, and each controller is tested by commanding the vehicle to follow this reference while maintaining stable and smooth motion. The simulated vehicle receives reference commands from the planning layer, including reference path, reference speed, and strategy-related priorities. The controller then computes the steering and acceleration commands, and the vehicle state is updated through the simulation model.

In this project, PID, ADRC, LQR, and MPC are considered as candidate execution-level controllers. PID is used as the baseline feedback controller because it is simple and easy to tune. ADRC is included because it was used in the earlier stage of the project to improve robustness against disturbance and model uncertainty. LQR is used as an optimal

Fig. 7. Simulated trajectory comparison on a closed racing track. The reference path is compared with the trajectories generated by PID, ADRC, LQR, and MPC.

state-feedback controller with a clear cost-function structure. MPC is considered as a predictive controller that can include constraints more naturally. The detailed controller design is discussed in the previous section, while this section focuses on how their performance is evaluated under the same simulation framework.

Fig. 7 shows an example trajectory comparison on a closed racing track. The reference path is shown together with the simulated trajectories of different controllers. The purpose of this figure is to show the tracking behavior visually. A better controller should stay close to the reference path while avoiding unnecessary oscillation or aggressive correction.

B. Performance Metrics

To compare the controllers fairly, we use a set of normalized performance metrics. These metrics are selected to reflect both low-level vehicle control and high-level racing strategy execution. The first metric is tracking error, which measures how far the vehicle deviates from the desired racing line:

$$E_{\text{track}} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{k=1}^T e_y^2(k), \quad (47)$$

where $e_y(k)$ is the lateral tracking error and T is the total number of simulation steps.

The heading error is defined as

$$E_{\text{heading}} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{k=1}^T e_\psi^2(k), \quad (48)$$

where $e_\psi(k)$ is the heading error between the vehicle heading and the reference path heading.

The control effort is defined as

$$E_{\text{control}} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{k=1}^T \|u(k)\|_2^2, \quad (49)$$

where $u(k)$ is the control input. This metric is used because a racing controller should not only be accurate, but also avoid unnecessary aggressive steering or acceleration commands.

Safety is evaluated by checking track boundary and constraint violation. A simplified safety penalty can be written as

$$E_{\text{safety}} = \sum_{k=1}^T \mathbf{1}\{p(k) \notin \mathcal{T}\} + \sum_{k=1}^T \mathbf{1}\{d(k) < d_{\min}\}, \quad (50)$$

where \mathcal{T} is the feasible track region, $d(k)$ is the distance to another vehicle or boundary, and d_{\min} is the minimum safety distance.

Since this project also studies strategy-driven racing, we define a strategy deviation metric:

$$E_{\text{strategy}} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{k=1}^T \|b(k) - b_{\text{des}}(k)\|_2^2, \quad (51)$$

where $b(k)$ represents the actual behavior of the vehicle, and $b_{\text{des}}(k)$ represents the desired behavior given by the strategy layer. For example, if the strategy is aggressive, the desired behavior may include higher reference speed and smaller time loss. If the strategy is conservative, the desired behavior may include smoother control input and larger safety margin.

To combine different metrics, each raw metric is normalized as

$$\bar{E}_m = \frac{E_m - E_m^{\min}}{E_m^{\max} - E_m^{\min}}, \quad (52)$$

where E_m is one metric value, and E_m^{\min} and E_m^{\max} are the best and worst values among all tested controllers. A lower normalized value means better performance for error or penalty metrics.

The overall strategy execution score is defined as

$$S = \sum_{m=1}^M w_m (1 - \bar{E}_m), \quad \sum_{m=1}^M w_m = 1, \quad (53)$$

where w_m is the weight of the m -th metric. This score is useful because it allows the project to compare controllers not only by one metric, but by a balanced combination of tracking, stability, safety, smoothness, and strategy consistency.

C. Controller Comparison

Fig. 8 shows a normalized comparison of different controllers across several simulation metrics. In this figure, lower values indicate better performance. PID is easy to implement and provides a useful baseline, but it usually has larger tracking and heading errors because it does not explicitly optimize a cost function. ADRC improves robustness and gives smoother behavior in some cases, especially when disturbance or model uncertainty is present. However, its performance still depends on tuning and observer behavior.

LQR gives better overall performance in this project because it directly balances state error and control effort through a cost function. This makes it easier to connect the controller with the strategy layer. For example, if the strategy requires smoother

Fig. 8. Normalized controller comparison across tracking error, heading error, control effort, safety penalty, and strategy deviation. Lower values indicate better performance.

Fig. 9. Normalized strategy execution score for different controllers. Higher values indicate better balanced performance across tracking, stability, smoothness, safety, and strategy consistency.

driving, the control weight can be increased. If the strategy requires more aggressive tracking, the state tracking weight can be increased. MPC also performs well, especially for safety-related constraints, because it predicts future states and can include constraints over a finite time horizon. However, MPC usually has higher computational cost than LQR.

Fig. 9 shows the normalized strategy execution score. This score combines several metrics into one weighted value. The goal is not to claim that one controller is always the best, but to show how each controller fits the strategy-driven racing framework. In this example, LQR and MPC achieve higher scores because they are more naturally connected to objective-based control. LQR is especially useful when real-time computation is important, while MPC is more powerful when constraints and future prediction are the main focus.

D. Discussion of Results

The simulation results support the main idea of this project: controller performance should not be judged only by path tracking. For autonomous racing, a controller also needs to

execute the intended racing strategy safely and smoothly. A controller that has low tracking error but produces aggressive or unstable control input may not be the best choice for a conservative strategy. Similarly, a controller that is smooth but too slow may not support an aggressive racing strategy.

PID and ADRC are useful because they helped us build the foundation of the project. They are easier to understand and implement, and they provide a clear baseline for testing. However, when the project moved toward strategy-driven racing, LQR and MPC became more suitable because they can directly include weights, objectives, and constraints. This makes them easier to connect with the upper strategy and planning layers.

Among the controllers considered, LQR provides a good balance between performance and computational simplicity. It is not as constraint-aware as MPC, but it is easier to implement and faster to compute. This makes it a practical choice for real-time autonomous racing simulation. MPC is still an important future direction because it can handle track boundaries, actuator limits, and safety constraints more directly. The main limitation is that it requires more computation, especially when the vehicle model and multi-agent interactions become more complex.

Overall, the simulation shows that the proposed framework can compare controllers in a more complete way. Instead of only asking which controller follows the path most accurately, the evaluation also asks which controller better supports the racing objective. This matches the main direction of the project: autonomous racing should be viewed as a strategy-driven multi-agent control problem, where the controller is the execution module inside a larger decision-making loop.

VII. CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS

Although this project gives us a clear framework for connecting racing strategy and controller execution, there are still several important challenges. Most of these challenges come from the same basic issue: autonomous racing is not only a mathematical control problem, but also a physical vehicle problem. A controller may look good in simulation, but the final behavior still needs to make sense for a real racing car.

The first challenge is vehicle modeling. In real racing environments such as Formula 1 or Indy-style racing, the physical model of the vehicle is extremely complicated. The vehicle behavior is affected by tire forces, aerodynamic downforce, load transfer, road friction, suspension dynamics, actuator delay, and many other details. It is almost impossible to include every factor in a simple project model. However, if the model is too simple, the simulation result may not fully represent the real vehicle behavior. This creates a difficult balance. We need a model that is detailed enough to capture the important racing behavior, but still simple enough to use for controller design, simulation, and comparison. In this project, our model mainly captures the basic motion, tracking error, control input, and strategy-level behavior. Therefore, one limitation is that the simulation cannot fully represent all physical effects of a high-speed racing vehicle.

The second challenge is the physical feasibility of the controller output. In simulation, a controller can sometimes generate steering, throttle, or braking commands that reduce tracking error but may not be realistic for an actual vehicle. For example, the steering command may change too quickly, the acceleration demand may be too aggressive, or the controller may require a response that exceeds the tire friction limit. This is especially important in racing, because high-speed cornering and sudden maneuvers can push the vehicle close to its physical limits. A controller should not only make the error small; it should also produce actions that a real car can reasonably execute. This means that constraints such as

$$|\delta_i(k)| \leq \delta_{\max}, \quad |\dot{\delta}_i(k)| \leq \dot{\delta}_{\max}, \quad (54)$$

and

$$a_{\min} \leq a_i(k) \leq a_{\max} \quad (55)$$

are not just mathematical details. They are necessary for judging whether the controller output is physically meaningful. In the current project, we considered control effort, smoothness, and safety penalties, but we did not fully verify every control action on a high-fidelity vehicle model or real hardware platform.

The third challenge is how to translate high-level strategy into low-level control decisions. The main idea of our framework is that a top-level team objective or consensus can guide the lower-level strategy, planning, and controller execution. However, the exact mapping between these layers is still difficult. For example, if the high-level strategy is aggressive, we still need to decide how much the reference speed should increase, how the safety margin should change, and how the LQR or MPC weights should be adjusted. If the high-level strategy is conservative, we also need a clear way to translate that idea into control weights, constraints, and reference commands. In other words, the logic from team consensus to

tactical decision to controller objective to vehicle input is the most important part of the strategy framework, but it is also one of the hardest parts to make rigorous.

Because of this, the current strategy layer should be understood as a structured framework rather than a fully automatic racing strategist. We can describe how a team objective influences the vehicle behavior, and we can use weights, constraints, and reference commands to connect strategy with control. However, we have not yet developed a complete method that automatically generates every tactical decision from the top-level consensus. This is an important limitation of the current work. For the strategy layer to become more practical, the relationships between different strategy levels need stronger logical and mathematical support.

Another limitation is that the project is still mainly simulation-based. Simulation is useful because it allows us to test ideas quickly and compare controllers under the same conditions. However, real racing includes more uncertainty than our simulation. Sensor noise, communication delay, tire degradation, changing road conditions, actuator limits, and

unpredictable opponent behavior can all affect the result. Also, the opponent and teammate interactions in our current framework are simplified. They help us study the structure of multi-agent racing, but they are not yet a complete model of real racing competition.

Overall, these challenges do not mean that the framework is not useful. Instead, they show where the project needs to improve before moving toward a more realistic autonomous racing system. The current work provides a foundation for connecting strategy, planning, and control, but future work must use a more complete vehicle model, more realistic actuator constraints, and a stronger strategy-to-control mapping. Without these improvements, the controller may perform well in simulation but still fail to represent realistic racing behavior.

VIII. FUTURE WORK

Based on the challenges discussed above, the next step of this project is to make the framework more realistic, more automatic, and easier to validate. The current project gives a basic structure for connecting racing strategy, planning, and control, but there is still a large gap between this simulation framework and a real autonomous racing system.

First, future work should improve the vehicle model. In this project, the model is simplified so that we can focus on controller comparison and strategy structure. However, real racing cars have much more complicated dynamics. Future models should include more details such as tire force, tire saturation, load transfer, aerodynamic effects, road friction, actuator delay, and speed-dependent handling behavior. A more realistic model would make the simulation results more meaningful and would also help us understand whether the controller behavior is actually reasonable for a physical vehicle.

Second, the controller output should be checked more carefully for physical feasibility. In the current project, we evaluate tracking error, stability, control effort, smoothness, and safety. In future work, the control input itself should be tested against more realistic actuator constraints. For example, the steering angle, steering rate, acceleration, braking force, and tire friction limit should all be considered. This is important because a controller may reduce tracking error in simulation but still produce commands that a real racing car cannot safely execute. A good racing controller should not only follow the path, but also generate actions that are physically possible and smooth enough for high-speed driving.

Third, the strategy-to-control mapping should be developed more rigorously. The main idea of this project is that a top-level team objective or consensus can guide the lower-level tactical decisions and controller execution. However, in the current framework, this relationship is still mostly designed by logic and interpretation. In future work, we want to make this mapping more automatic. For example, an aggressive strategy should clearly change the reference speed, safety margin, and controller weights. A conservative strategy should increase

safety requirements and reduce aggressive control actions. This relationship can be written in a general form as

$$(Q_i, R_i, d_i^{\text{safe}}, v_i^{\text{ref}}) = \Phi(\gamma, z_i, \mathcal{I}_i), \quad (56)$$

where γ is the team objective, z_i is the strategy state of vehicle i , and \mathcal{I}_i is the information available to the vehicle. This mapping would allow high-level strategy to directly influence the controller parameters and planning references in a clearer way.

Fourth, MPC and constrained optimal control should be explored more deeply. LQR is useful because it has a clear cost function and relatively low computational cost, which makes it suitable for real-time simulation. However, MPC is more powerful when constraints and prediction are important. In future work, MPC can be used to handle track boundaries, actuator limits, safety distance, and opponent prediction more directly. The main difficulty is computation time, especially when the model becomes more realistic and multiple vehicles are included. Therefore, future work should also consider faster optimization methods or simplified MPC formulations that can still run in real time.

Finally, the framework should be tested on more realistic platforms. At the current stage, most of the validation is simulation-based. In the future, it would be useful to test the framework in a higher-fidelity simulator, a ROS-based environment, a Quanser platform, or a small-scale autonomous racing vehicle. Hardware-in-the-loop testing would also help us understand whether the controller outputs are realistic and whether the strategy layer can work under sensor noise, delay, and real actuator limits. These tests would make the project more practical and would provide stronger evidence for the proposed strategy-driven autonomous racing framework.

Overall, the future direction is to move from a clear conceptual and simulation framework toward a more realistic autonomous racing system. The main goal is not only to make the vehicle track a path, but also to make sure that high-level racing strategy can be translated into safe, smooth, and physically meaningful vehicle behavior.

IX. TEAM MEMBER CONTRIBUTIONS

This project was completed through collaboration among all team members. The main responsibilities were divided as follows:

- **Zhishan Wang:** System design, overall strategy framework, simulation, controller integration, and controller design.
- **Kaijie Zhu:** Controller design, paper writing, and visualization.
- **Zheng Qing:** ROS-based simulation and related simulation implementation.
- **Kieran Venkat Desireddi:** Multi-vehicle competition strategy research and strategy design.
- **Jacob Junjie Zhang:** Controller design and simulation.
- **Brian Sam Lee:** Physical model improvement and vehicle model refinement.

Overall, the team work was divided across system-level design, controller development, simulation validation, and strategy modeling. This division allowed the project to connect different parts of the autonomous racing problem into one shared framework.

X. CONCLUSION

This two-semester project studied autonomous racing from both a controller design viewpoint and a strategy-driven system viewpoint. At the beginning, our focus was mainly on low-level vehicle control. We used PID as a baseline controller and explored ADRC to improve robustness and trajectory recovery. As the project continued, we realized that autonomous racing is not only about making a vehicle follow a path. A racing vehicle also needs to respond to objectives, risk preferences, teammate behavior, opponent behavior, and strategy-level decisions. This pushed the project toward a larger framework that connects strategy, planning, and control.

In this paper, we presented a hierarchical autonomous racing framework that organizes the system into a strategy layer, a tactical planning layer, and a control execution layer. We defined the main vehicle states, control inputs, reference commands, and information flow in the system. We also introduced a multi-agent racing strategy framework, where vehicles can exchange local information and respond to a shared team objective. The consensus-inspired structure was used as a simple way to describe how multiple vehicles can coordinate without forcing them to behave exactly the same.

The simulation and evaluation part showed how this framework can be used to compare different controllers under shared performance metrics. Instead of only looking at tracking error, the evaluation also considered stability, control effort, safety, smoothness, and strategy consistency. PID and ADRC were useful for building the foundation of the project and understanding basic tracking behavior. LQR and MPC were more suitable for the later strategy-driven framework because they can connect controller behavior with cost functions, constraints, and strategy-dependent weights. In particular, LQR provided a practical balance between performance and computational simplicity, while MPC remained an important future direction for constraint-aware and predictive racing control.

There are still important limitations in this work. The current model is simplified, and it cannot fully represent the physical details of a real racing car. The strategy-to-control mapping also needs to be made more rigorous, especially if the framework is expected to generate tactical decisions automatically from a high-level team objective. In addition, the current validation is mainly simulation-based, so future work should include more realistic vehicle models, actuator constraints, high-fidelity simulation, and possible hardware testing.

Overall, this project helped us move from asking how to control one autonomous racing vehicle to asking how an autonomous racing system should make and execute racing decisions. The final framework is not a complete racing

Fig. 10. Summary of the project development from low-level controller design to a strategy-aware multi-agent autonomous racing framework.

solution, but it provides a clear foundation for future work on strategy-aware, multi-agent autonomous racing control.

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